

Feasibility of Self-Supervised Super-Resolution for Dynamic Hyperpolarized ^{13}C MRI Using SSDU

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Introduction:

Hyperpolarized [$1\text{-}^{13}\text{C}$] pyruvate MRI has enabled non-invasive assessment of cerebral pyruvate and lactate metabolism in healthy human subjects (1). However, the spatial resolution of current acquisitions remains limited, motivating the development of methods that can improve spatial representation without requiring additional scan time. Although deep learning-based super-resolution methods could improve image quality, their application is challenging due to the general unavailability of high-resolution reference data (2). This is particularly problematic for dynamic ^{13}C studies, where only low-resolution data is available, making supervised training impossible. Self-supervised learning via data undersampling (SSDU) enables neural networks to be trained directly from acquired k-space data, eliminating the need for fully sampled reference images (3). Although SSDU has been widely used for reconstruction problems, it is unclear whether the same concept can be applied to super-resolution. In this study, we explore this possibility in dynamic, hyperpolarized ^{13}C brain imaging.

Methods:

The study was performed on dynamic hyperpolarized ^{13}C brain datasets containing pyruvate, lactate, bicarbonate, and alanine images. Rather than training separate models for each metabolite, all metabolites were used simultaneously during training. The acquired spiral k-space data were divided into SSDU training (Θ) and loss (Λ) subsets. The Θ samples were reconstructed with an adjoint NUFFT operator to produce low-resolution 40×40 images. These images were used as input to a convolutional neural network, which generated super-resolved 80×80 images. The super-resolved images were then projected back to the acquired trajectory using a high-resolution NUFFT forward operator. Training was performed by comparing the predicted k-space samples with the held-out Λ measurements, following the SSDU framework (Figure 1).

To increase the number of training examples, multiple dynamic time points were included. Because late dynamic frames often contained very little signal, an SNR-based filtering step was applied and only time points above a predefined threshold were retained for training.

Results:

The proposed framework was trained using dynamic hyperpolarized ^{13}C brain datasets that contained pyruvate, lactate, bicarbonate, and alanine. Multiple time points were included during training, and low-SNR frames were excluded using an SNR-based filtering strategy. After SNR-based filtering, only dynamic frames with sufficient signal support were retained for training and validation. Figure 2 shows representative results for pyruvate and lactate. The first column shows the reconstruction obtained from the SSDU training subset, the second shows the super-resolved network output, and the third shows the reconstruction obtained from the full dataset. For both metabolites, the super-resolved images preserve the overall spatial distribution observed in the full-data reconstruction. The dominant pyruvate structure is visible in all three reconstructions. The network output exhibits a smoother spatial representation than the reconstruction obtained from the Θ subset alone. Similar behavior is observed for lactate, where the main signal distribution remains consistent across the three reconstructions. The framework converged stably during training and produced visually plausible, high-resolution metabolite maps for all investigated datasets.

Discussion and Conclusion:

The proposed framework demonstrates the feasibility of extending SSDU to a super-resolution setting for dynamic hyperpolarized ^{13}C MRI. Training was performed entirely using acquired k-space measurements, eliminating the need for high-resolution reference data.

Pyruvate reconstructions exhibited the most consistent spatial structure across the examined datasets. Lactate remained noticeably noisier, likely due to its lower SNR and reduced signal support compared with pyruvate. This highlights a key challenge in applying self-supervised super-resolution to weak metabolic signals.

Since high-resolution ground truth data is unavailable, this work should be considered a feasibility study rather than a quantitative validation of super-resolution performance. Future work will focus on validation through controlled degradation experiments, the incorporation of additional datasets, and the investigation of approaches that more fully exploit the temporal information available in dynamic acquisitions. These preliminary results demonstrate the feasibility of physics-informed, self-supervised super-resolution for dynamic, hyperpolarized ^{13}C MRI and provide a foundation for future development and validation.

Figure 1. Schematic overview of the proposed SSDU-based super-resolution framework for dynamic hyperpolarized ^{13}C MRI. Multi-metabolite low-resolution reconstructions are transformed into super-resolved images and trained using a physics-informed SSDU loss computed on held-out k-space measurements.

Figure 2: Representative Pyruvate and Lactate Reconstructions from a Dynamic Hyperpolarized ^{13}C Brain Dataset. The first column shows the adjoint reconstruction obtained from the SSDU training subset (Θ), which was used to generate the network input. The second column shows the super-resolved network output (80×80). The third column shows the adjoint reconstruction obtained from the full k-space dataset acquired and is included only as a visual reference. All images are displayed after independent normalization to emphasize spatial distribution rather than absolute signal intensity.

References:

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